

ONLINE EDUCATION AND BUSINESS SIMULATION IN ENTREPRENEURIAL COMPETENCIES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to verify the effectiveness of the online education and business simulation in entrepreneurial competencies of Senior High School. This paper has studied how online education during the crisis and business simulation program as specialized subject in senior high can enhance the entrepreneurial competencies of the learners. This study was conducted on Accountancy, Business and Management students who attended the program as a final requirement for the curriculum. The results of the questionnaire survey were tested the effectiveness of both online education and business simulation, the level of their entrepreneurial competencies and their significant relationships by using product Pearson r. According to the research analysis, online education and business were perceived by the students as highly effective while their level of entrepreneurial competencies was found to be advanced. However, online education and business simulation program found no significant relationship to the entrepreneurial competencies of students. The results of this study suggested that education on the new normal should focus more on exploring how it could meet individual learners' needs and provide differentiated online instructions through the course design. It should also create a learning environment that would allow students to practice realistic scenarios related to their programs of study, and also applicable and easily adjustable to change of circumstance as required by the changing environment.

Keywords: online education, business simulation, entrepreneurial competencies